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Transforming the learning and educational culture at a university

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INTRODUCTION

New students enrolling in universities in the 2020-tale have lived their whole life in the middle of rich interactive digital resources and services. Using Internet and available online resources are self-evident parts of learning for almost all of them regardless of

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their background. Traditional classroom-based educational models from primary school to universities are heavily challenged in this new digital environment. On the other hand, digitalization is also a strong asset that provides universities wide opportunities to enrich students' learning experience, both on campus and in distance learning. It can provide students access to novel rich interactive learning resources, better facilities for student-student and student-teacher communication, and more versatile feedback on their exercises and projects. Digitalization can also support changing teacher's role from a lecturer towards a coach. However, these benefits can be achieved only, if university teachers truly adopt the available new tools and methods to use them. Creating new digital content, such as online videos, interactive e-books, automatic assessment tools or virtual reality resources may have a high learning curve for many teachers, who already struggle in the pressure of time management and increasing workloads. Moreover, adopting such resources also challenges teachers to change their pedagogical practices, because classroom pedagogies can rarely be transformed into online practices as such. For example, research on how students view online lecture videos in MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) showed that the length of videos that most students are willing to view, is around only 5-6 minutes [4]. This is very far from the duration of lectures, which are widely given in lecture halls.

Aalto University, with 11000 full time Bachelor's and Master's level students and 4000 faculty and staff members and researchers, is the leading university in Finland in the areas of technology, business and arts & design. The mission of the university is to *"build competitive edge by combining knowledge from different disciplines to identify and solve complex challenges, and to educate future visionaries and experts"* [2]. When the university defined its strategy for years 2016-2020, it identified one of the key goals as: *"Develop and deploy forerunner digital learning solutions to improve learning outcomes."* The university decided to invest an order of 10M€ to support this goal over these years, and a new 5-year project Aalto Online Learning (A!OLE)² was launched in the beginning of 2016. The goal of the project is to develop novel digital learning resources in all fields of the university, support building new pedagogical models for applying them, as well as develop new services for teachers to support their work in creating and adopting new digital learning tools and resources [1]. From the beginning it was stated that the goal is *not* to proceed towards fully online education; instead, the goal is to develop solutions that allow combining the best practices in both online and classroom learning.

In this paper, we present the experiences of the first two years of the A!OLE project and discuss our approaches to create a cultural change in the university. The main volume of the A!OLE comprises pilot projects that develop novel resources and pedagogies in different fields. This is supported by active workshops, which build teachers' competences in various areas of online education and at the same time strongly support networking with colleagues to build a new teacher community. We analyse a set of 24 pilot projects, covering their initial goals and expectations and contrast them with their experiences later on. Thus, we seek to build a holistic picture about the results of the whole project.

²<https://onlinelearning.aalto.fi/>

Our research questions are:

- 1) What were teachers' initial challenges and/or motivations for initiating a development project (AIOLE project),
- 2) What were the concrete development actions that the teachers took?

RELATED WORK

Universities are increasingly active in organising activities and support for enabling e-learning and online learning settings for their courses. These activities range from projects and hubs to service points and centres, some of which are briefly discussed below.

The EPFL Center for Digital Education (CEDE)³ serves teachers via the production team of MOOCS Factory and conducts research related to online learning. The Rolex Learning Center provides inspiring spaces for CEDE to operate at. Initiating a development of a MOOC at EPFL starts from a submitted application, after which the production team will handle and help with the actual production and operation of the MOOC. Our open call for idea proposals in AIOLE project is certainly related to their model but it is more widely looking for any kind of online/blended learning ideas, and the support they might need, accordingly.

In USA, the HarvardX⁴ is a strategic initiative of the Harvard University “*to enable faculty to build and create open online learning experiences for residential and online use, and to enable groundbreaking research in online pedagogies*”. This is very much a shared goal of our AIOLE project, as well. MITx, the initiative of MIT, says⁵ their “*goals include expanding access to quality educational opportunities worldwide, enhancing on-campus education, and advancing understanding of teaching and learning through research*”. HarvardX and MITx have published statistics about their online offerings: already in their “4 Year Report” they report about significant activities, including for instance 4.5 million participants having 28-million participant hours at their courses [3]. The Explore Digital Learning -initiative of the Northwestern University offers “*to connect with other instructors and find ideas to enhance teaching and learning*”, also a very shared idea with our project. Stanford | Online⁶ is also a large scale and well-known activity of Stanford university online courses, and has clearly inspired many of their central stakeholders and teachers to get involved. Further on, The University of Minnesota offers⁷ openly online a number of useful resources for developing online learning facilities.

Another related initiative, the TU Delft Online Learning Experience (OLE) [5] is a pedagogical model that serves as a basis for activities with TU Delft to ensure the quality when developing online learning for their courses. To further support teachers TU Delft operates an Online Learning Hub⁸, which is essentially a portal guiding its

³ <https://moocs.epfl.ch/>

⁴ <https://courses.harvardxplus.harvard.edu>

⁵ <https://openlearning.mit.edu/beyond-campus/mitx-edx-moocs>

⁶ <https://online.stanford.edu>

⁷ <https://cei.umn.edu/online-learning/resources-support-online-and-blended-learning>

⁸ <https://onlinelearninghub.tudelft.nl>

users to prepare online courses. Further on, also a center type of activity, but more focused on research is the Learnt⁹, Center for Digital Learning Technology at DTU in Denmark.

A!OLE PROJECT

Aalto Online Learning is a strategic project at Aalto university for years 2016-2020. Its leadership includes a professor level academic chair and a full-time project manager, who plan and coordinate activities and budgets, accordingly. The funding decisions are made by the vice president of education. The overall funding has been around 2-2,5 M€ annually of which roughly 70% is used for pilot projects and the rest for various support services.

The main project supports and funds pilot projects, which are solicited through *calls for idea proposals* for the faculty and staff members and students twice a year. The call is – on purpose – a light-weight process. Instead of requesting a complete project plan from the applicants, we request that the proposals are submitted through a web form that includes a number of questions directing the applicants to consider their initial problem in teaching or learning, how online learning could help resolving it, how the pilot could be evaluated and what kind of support is needed. The answers form a basis for an interview where we elaborate the challenges and plans further, identify possible synergies with other pilots, and discuss funding needs. It is notable that not all proposals request funding, but only wish to join the A!OLE teacher community and get support from the core project. Moreover, while projects are called A!OLE pilots, most of them target to build new resources and/or methods that will be used in real courses immediately when the pilot project is completed. That is, pilots are not just for testing ideas, but applying them to support or revise education in courses in full scale.

We support the accepted pilot projects in several ways. Weekly voluntary workshops are available to learn and discuss novel tools and methods for online learning. Pilot leaders are encouraged to attend the workshops that best fit to their needs. Pilot projects developing similar resources are combined into thematic groups, which have their own meetings. These groups include topics like blended learning, video production, online textbooks, automatic assessment, gamification, online social interaction, augmented reality and virtual reality. Twice a year we organize a large gala type celebration, which is open to all people in the university and where results achieved in completed pilots as well as work-in-progress are demonstrated. Overall these activities have a goal of building the A!OLE *coaching network*, where teachers can exchange ideas and get support and encouragement from each other when developing practical skills.

DATA COLLECTION

We collected the data for this paper with an online-survey from A!OLE pilot proposals, which received funding in the academic year 2016-2017. The survey was designed and sent to pilot leaders in January 2018, and 25 responses were received by the end of February 2018. One respondent did not give permission to use the answers for research purpose and thus our data pool consists of 24 answers to the survey. The

⁹ <http://www.learnt.dtu.dk>

online survey consisted of 20 different mostly open-ended questions, in which most significant areas covered eventual changes in education, experiences gained, successes, challenges and results. Furthermore, we inquired in particular how the projects had supported students' learning. One important question for the pilots was the level and quality of support received from the A!OLE-project. A minor part of the questions were Likert-type polls.

The pilots in the data pool focused on bachelor and master level degree programme education in Aalto schools. Language teaching as service education for the entire university was also well represented. Most pilots concerned developing a single existing or new course. However, several ones developed two or many courses, typically in bachelor education. Student numbers in pilot courses and education varied from under 10 till some thousands (in case where many large courses were combined under one pilot). The typical size of a single pilot course ranged from 30 to 100 students. Most academic leaders in the pilots were lecturers and professors. One pilot had a team of experts with also some students as a resource.

The data was rather rich, and the respondents in general had described well their own pilot's experiences. However, a few pilot leaders mentioned that their project was still on-going, and they could not yet properly respond to all questions.

METHODOLOGY

We used qualitative, inductive content analysis [6], a systematic analysis method to extract and summarize the essence of the open-ended responses that were related to the motivation and goal of each A!OLE project. Two authors of this paper split the data into two so that each researcher analysed 12 survey responses. However, in the cases where one researcher was unsure how the utterance should be interpreted, the two researchers discussed together until they reached consensus. The two researchers did together the final stage of the analysis, where we sought for the common denominators.

At the beginning of the analysis process, the two authors read through all survey answers marking sentences that conveyed ideas and themes relating to our two research questions. The essence of each utterance was then summarised into few words and utterances that conveyed similar content were placed into the same pile. Next, we read through all the phrases in one pile and sought for a common denominator (raising the abstraction level of how we talk about our data), which then became the name of the category. In the final phase of the analysis, we took a closer look at the categories to identify what each category seemed to focus on (student, teacher, teaching approach, ...) to emphasize the root reason or motivation for doing the A!OLE pilot project.

RESULTS

In our first research question we were interested in teachers' initial motivation for initiating a development project (A!OLE pilot project). Our results suggest that the teachers' motivation can be divided into five large categories.

Student: The aim of the project is to find ways to support and enhance students' understanding and skills. For instance, in one pilot the teachers developed

"... virtual reality molecular modelling application to aid students' understanding of the three-dimensional atomic-level structure of molecules and matter."

In another pilot the aim was

"... to expand the students' ability to communicate scientific data through other than written media."

Some pilots focused on improving students' learning experience, for example:

"To try out different technologies that would support learning and teaching, the course integrated elements from game design to create a gameful learning experience."

Teacher: The aim of the project is to enhance teachers' skills and knowledge on how to best teach/organize the course or to make teachers' work more efficient. One project leader expressed the essence of this category as follows

"... we have had a chance to make interesting technical and pedagogical experiments to understand how to best teach our students ..."

Several different teachers reported that they had experimented with, for instance, internet streaming, online exams, and students' self-made videos as a means to report the results of a project work.

Community: The aim is to change the way teaching and learning related actions/processes are carried out, e.g., the way feedback is given. This includes also support and help from peer teachers and network, which has been gradually developed during the project's existence. One response formulated this, as follows:

"To change the feedback culture from static to dynamic."

Teaching approach: The aim is to make a transfer from one teaching approach to another, e.g., from traditional to flipped classroom. The common theme among the pilots in this category is that the teachers want to rethink their use of the classroom time. One teacher perceived his/her A!OLE project as

"... a resource for flipped learning to help increase time available for teacher student interaction."

Another teacher told that he had turned

"... all lectures into gamified online modules and focussing classroom time on applications."

Tools: The aim is to develop/test technologies and tools that aid the teaching and learning process. The focus of a number of A!OLE projects was mostly on developing and experimenting with technology that might help students with their studies. For instance, one teacher listed the following concrete actions s/he had made:

"... implementing and producing scalable automatic grading back ends, developing the automatic feedback provided by the back ends."

Because developing rich interactive content is not technically trivial, one pilot

"... developed processes to design, create, and maintain interactive learning materials for programming courses."

Our second research question concerned "What were the concrete development actions that the teachers took? [in their AIOLE pilot]". The actions were manifold varying from developing concrete tools and systems to trying out new teaching methods or new ways to organize the course.

Many pilots created novel types of online content. Creating online videos, online episodes and podcasts was popular. Virtual reality content was generated in some pilots, and one form of this was utilizing 360-degree videos to support students' familiarization to laboratories and their facilities. Streaming lectures to the Internet was also one method.

One specific area in creating new content was developing rich interactive content, such as modelling applications, tools connecting the lab equipment and simulation models, or automatic feedback and grading tools. One aspect here was improving the usability of the tools from students', instructors' or maintenance point of view. Building online exams was also one concrete action.

Some projects ended up developing new teaching methods, e.g. using course design cards¹⁰, or building student collaboration between two Aalto schools. More radical approaches ended up redesigning the course completely. For instance, in one pilot the role of students changed radically towards active creators of the course content, and in another one they turned all lectures into gamified online modules and focussed classroom time on applications.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data from the survey, the authors conclude that the AIOLE-project has already now well enlarged and supported developing blended learning and teaching at Aalto University. While this sample data was collected only from one third of the ongoing or finished pilot projects after the first two years, the results demonstrate many very good examples of novel online and blended learning resources and how they have been or will be integrated with classroom teaching.

¹⁰ These cards support innovative design as follows. The cards identify various dimensions of course design by setting questions and possible answers to a teacher: What learning theory will your course be based on? Perhaps Constructivism or Connectivism? What learning approach will you take, perhaps case-based learning or challenge-based learning? Which instructional methods will you use? Perhaps peer teaching or demonstration? What is the course frame? Will your course be a self-paced or instructor-paced? Which platform will you select? A commercial MOOC or will you create your own platform? When it comes to content production, which online tools and techniques will you use? Webinars, wiki, blogs, quizzes, podcasts? How about monetization, are you aiming to generate profit and if so what is the business model? Selling additional content, selling certificates, subscription? How will you market your course? Through teaser content, high-profile people, social media? See also: <https://www.slideshare.net/mileht/idbm-challenge-manual>

The results also suggest that the majority of the teaching personnel in the pilots have gained more encouragement and new visions to develop their teaching. In many pilots, cooperation between teaching staff and students has been strengthened as well, when students have been a part of the pilot. Yet, many respondents were still slightly cautious to assess longer-term impacts when their own pilots were on-going.

We are currently defining clear processes to support teachers in building various types of online learning content, and we have recognized several issues to be addressed in the future. How to support the maintenance and further development of the created online resources when the pilot project funding period ends? How to implement more systematic blended learning development in degree programme level and how to support the role of degree programme leaders in this? How to support expanding the new teaching and learning culture in departments and get new teachers involved in redesigning their education?

We would like to gain more insight into how the pilots and various new methods, tools, platforms etc. may have had impact on teachers' pedagogical growth and development. We acknowledge that a survey could provide us only an initial overview of the impact of the A!OLE project on teachers' work. Therefore, in the next phase we deepen our data collection in terms of interviewing teachers who gave their permission for the interviews further qualitative analysis of this richer data. Moreover, we could expect that in the subsequent phase the pilots would have received more experiences on students' learning results, and also on the eventual impact on curriculum development in programmes or departments.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kauppinen, T., Malmi, L. (2017). Aalto Online Learning - a pathway to reforming education at the Aalto University. Proc. of 23rd EUNIS Annual congress, pp. 212-221.
- [2] Aalto University Vision, Mission and Strategies 2016–2020.
<http://www.aalto.fi/en/about/strategy/>
- [3] Chuang, I. and Ho, A. (2006), HarvardX and MITx: Four Years of Open Online Courses - Fall 2012-Summer 2016. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2889436>
- [4] Guo, P. J., Kim, J., & Rubin, R. (2014). How video production affects student engagement: An empirical study of MOOC videos. Proc. of the first ACM conference on Learning@scale conference, ACM, pp. 41-50.
- [5] Jorge, N., Van Valkenburg, W., Dopper, S. (2016), The TU Delft Online Learning Experience: From Theory to Practice. In Teixeira, Szucs and Mazar (2016). Proc. of EDEN 2016 Annual Conference, pp. 643-649.
- [6] Mayring, P. (2000). Qualitative Content Analysis. FQS Forum: Qualitative Social Research, 1(2), Art. 20.